

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

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AC-DC and DC-DC converters analysis and definition for their application in a real Distribution Grid

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Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
AFE	Active Front End
HVAC	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
IED	Intelligent Electronic Devices
RCD	Residual Current Detector
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
OPF	Optimum Power Flow
BMS	Battery Management System
DC	Direct Current
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EV	Electric Vehicle
LV	Low Voltage
MV	Medium Voltage
SCADA	Supervisory control and data acquisition
V2G	Vehicle-To-Grid
PV	Photovoltaic
ASGC	AIT Smart Grid Converter
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
RPF	Reverse Power Flow
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report describes the steps for properly sizing and selecting, depending on expected performance, safety and operators training, the DC components that will be integrated in the Terni Pilot infrastructure. The demonstrator in Terni is aiming at achieving the HYPERRIDE objectives, demonstrating the benefits over the conventional Alternating Current (AC) grids. especially by the integrating renewables in hybrid AC/DC grids. This is enabling the identification of solutions to overcome barriers for a successful roll-out of new infrastructure concepts throughout Europe.

The proposed configuration and list of components will be based on the targeted functional features of the Terni demonstrator, previously defined, and will be used for the system level modeling and simulation, in Task 4.2 “LVDC virtual microgrid model and simulation”, in WP4.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This deliverable presents an analysis of AC/DC and DC/DC converters, recommended for the application in a real DC Distribution Grid. The converters will allow the integration of the selected Distributed Energy Resources (DER) and loads, together with a control system which implements the main functional requirements defined in Work Package (WP) 8. The DC microgrid is built as a sub-grid of the existing AC grid in Terni. The document will provide a description and the product specification of the recommended converter.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Following the executive summary and the introduction, Section 2 describes the use cases which will be studied in the AC/DC microgrid built in Terni. In Section 3, we included a list of the functional features required to implement the use cases. This list will be prioritised in features that are critical to the safe operation of the system (as required), features that are addressing the user needs and features that may enable future developments, such as energy communities.

Further, the report describes (in Section 4) the proposed DC microgrid configuration, with the introduction of the sources, loads, converter types and bus configuration. Section 5 is describing the recommended control strategy, protection coordination and grounding whereas Section 6 includes a list with the possible components (converters, sources and loads), including specifications. The conclusions and the future steps are presented in Section 7.

2 Hybrid AC/DC Microgrid Use Case

The Terni pilot is demonstrating the benefits of a more modular (cellular) smart hybrid DC/AC grid, with a decentralized operation of a grid including Medium Voltage (MV) and Low Voltage (LV) distribution. The intended objectives are to increase the grid operation efficiency, to have a better control over the power flow between the MV and the LV sections, and to mitigate the cyber-security risks.

Figure 1: The 4 substation configuration installed in Terni, and the DC connection points.

The proposed pilot infrastructure comprises of a distribution feeder (2 200 m length) connecting a HV/MV station with 4 MV/LV substations (called ASM, MAZZOCCHIO, CELI and SCOV), as shown in Figure 1. This feeder hosts a significant intermittent local electricity generation from PV panel array (490 kW peak power). The PV array is overdimensioned, resulting in a significant, uncontrolled energy generation, so that there is a large Reverse Power Flow (RPF) in the primary substation. This power flow creates instability of the system, and results in overvoltage on the feeder, uncertainty of protection coordination, increased fault currents, and incorrect operation of equipment.

The activity in WP8 will build a DC branch of the existing AC grid configuration, as shown in Figure 2. The DC microgrid will demonstrate how an increase in the sustainability and resiliency of the hybrid grid, by connecting renewable generation with energy storage and allowing smart Electric Vehicle (EV) charging. The DC control system in the Terni demonstrator can be used to facilitate the integration of PV and EV charging, while proving the concept for grid services enabled by DC integration and back-up support for critical loads.

Figure 2: The AC grid in Terni, with the proposed DC branch to be implemented.

3 Targeted Safety and Functional Features

The DC branch will implement a series of functional features that will demonstrate the benefits of integrating DER with a control system that will allow the optimisation of power flows. This system will address the user requirements such as the optimisation of the self-consumption and the minimisation of the energy bill and will mitigate the impact of EV charging on the AC grid supply.

3.1 Basic Smart Grid Functions

Some of the most recommended functions to be implemented by the converters and the control system in the Terni demo are described in the next paragraphs.

3.1.1 Bidirectional power flows

One of the most important functional features of a DC branch in a hybrid AC/DC grid is the capability for bidirectional power flow through the Point of Common Coupling (PCC). The branch includes renewable generation which is primarily used by the DC connected loads. If, in the DC microgrid, the consumption of the loads is larger than the power provided by the sources, the power will flow from the AC side to the DC side. In case of low consumption, the surplus energy should be transferred to the AC side, to lower the overall energy consumption from the main substation. For the DC assets, in addition to the battery connection, for which the bidirectional flow is mandatory, the EV charger will also implement Vehicle-To-Grid (V2G) functionality, for increased benefits.

3.1.2 Seamless Connection to the AC Grid

The bidirectional power flow through the PCC should be implemented (by the control algorithm) such that the change in the direction of the energy flow should be automatic, based on power requirements of the loads in the DC branch. As soon as the power demand on the DC branch exceeds the local generation, the control system should switch the direction of the flow of energy from the AC grid to the DC branch, without disrupting the asset operation.

3.1.3 Black Start Capability

In case of a black-out, or a malfunction of the AC grid that will recommend the disconnection of the DC branch from the main AC grid, the DC branch should be able to start operating on the local generation (PV or battery power, or both). The control system should be able to control the pre-charging of the DC bus, as well as the transient voltage and current variations, until the DC microgrid reaches a stable operating point.

3.1.4 Critical Loads (DC and AC) Resilience (Back-up Function)

In addition to the black-start function, the DC microgrid should be able to power some critical AC loads (heat pumps for office space heating and cooling).

3.1.5 Basic Protection and Personal Safety

The DC branch should have protection capabilities against over-current (short circuit fault) and transient over-voltage, to protect the electrical devices and prevent electrical fires, and residual current protection, for preventing life threatening events. The risk of electric shock can arise when live segments are exposed. To mitigate this risk, the DC grid needs an effective earthing and fault detection protection system that can quickly resolve the fault before someone is hurt (IEC, 2005). IEC60479 (IEC, 2005) characterises the effects of electric currents on humans. The level of the current flowing through the human body depends on its impedance. Four time-current regions are categorised as follows (IEC, 2005):

- DC-1: minor sensations are felt;
- DC-2: muscles may involuntarily contract;
- DC-3: strong muscle contractions and adverse heart effects occur;
- DC-4: critical effects can occur which can result in death, depending on the time of exposure to the current.

It is therefore essential to select DC voltage levels and protection devices, such as Residual Current Detector (RCD), with sufficiently fast acting performance that limit the exposure to body currents. It is recommended (Štěpán, 2017) that voltages under 50 V DC do not present danger to humans (assuming a body impedance of 1 k Ω , therefore a threshold current of 50 mA). There are dedicated training courses organised for electrical workers by the regulatory bodies in many countries. These courses are usually updated to include safety voltage and current levels for DC power systems.

3.1.6 Grounding and Corrosion Prevention

One of the most important requirements for a DC microgrid is the grounding strategy, defining the grounding configuration and grounding device (grounding impedance). The strategy affects leakage currents, common-mode voltages, personnel and equipment safety, energy supply reliability, and protection requirements (Mohammadi, Badrkhani Ajaei, & Stevens, 2019). In addition, improper grounding configuration can create corrosion currents through the metal reinforcement of concrete in buildings (Liu, Jiang, Zhang, Mei, & Zheng, 2017), leading to serious building integrity issues. More information on the grounding configurations in DC microgrids is presented in Section 5.

3.1.7 Distributed Control vs. Central Control

The first level of control can be implemented without communication between nodes. The control feedback comes from the voltage of the DC bus. This method can be used for basic stability of the grid, for operating voltage and power flow ranges around a certain operating point. Additional control layers, based on a central controller, can be implemented for power flow optimisation (minimum consumption from AC, preserve battery life, self consumption from all PV panels - AC and DC side) over the AC/DC grid system and ancillary services capability.

3.1.8 Selective Feeder Protection

As the DC branch is connected to the AC grid, any fault on the DC side will affect the feeder. The protection coordination should be able to detect the fault and disconnect the feeder that may be affected (rapid increase in the AC current). In case of multiple feeders to the DC microgrid, the selective protection procedure can maintain the connection to the unaffected feeders and minimise the impact of the fault.

3.2 Additional Smart Grid Features

In addition, there are more complex functions that would enhance the benefits of the DC smart grid, but will probably not be included in the demo.

3.2.1 Protection Coordination and Selectivity

More than the basic protection, which disconnects all power sources in case of a fault, a protection coordination algorithm can be proposed, to ensure the safety of the system without disrupting its functionality. The control system may act automatically to de-energise the system, disconnect the faulty branches and re-energise. In more advanced implementations, the fault location is detected using sensors or Intelligent Electronic Devices (IED) and only the faulty section of the grid is disconnected, for an increased system resilience. This capability requires fast communication between the local control nodes, for automatic fault management, service restoration and maintenance.

3.2.2 Smart Metering and Monitoring

The benefits of the DC grid can be enhanced if the power flow and consumption decisions (such as smart EV charging and load shedding) are based on real time monitoring of the grid. In addition, the energy transactions between the renewable generation on the DC part of the grid and the AC grid, and further to the public grid, cannot be implemented without the use of smart meters, which can communicate with the Distribution System Operator (DSO) and allow the monetisation of the service.

3.2.3 ICT Features and Cyber Security Protection

Many safety features, such as coordinated protection, fault identification, service restoration, as well as power flow optimisation can be implemented through fast communication and edge computing nodes. However, the connectivity increases the risk for cyberattacks, therefore suitable cyber security measures must be considered.

4 Proposed DC Microgrid Configuration

The proposed configuration of the DC branch is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The proposed configuration of the DC microgrid.

The DC microgrid demonstrator includes common assets, to enable testing of various use cases: minimizing the amount of energy requested from the AC side (using the PV production and battery storage), smart EV charging, demand response and peak shaving. The main components of the demo are:

1. DER: photovoltaic panels, battery storage and EV charger with V2G capability;
2. DC and AC controllable loads: charging battery and EV, lighting, Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC), possibly heat pump;
3. Power electronics converters: buck-boost DC/DC converters for battery and EV charger, boost DC/DC for the photovoltaic connection, active front end for the AC feeders' connection, DC/AC inverter for critical AC loads;
4. DC protection devices: fuses and DC circuit breakers (solid state or hybrid fast breakers);
5. Local and central controllers, to implement the control strategy.

The local controllers are needed for a manufacturer agnostic approach when the primary controllers of the converters are not user programmable.

5 Microgrid Control, Protection Coordination, and Grounding Configuration

The main benefits of a microgrid (DER integration, self-consumption, decentralized generation) are enabled by the local monitoring and control system, which allows the optimisation of the power flows and of the power exchange between the microgrid and the main grid (AC or hybrid AC/DC).

5.1 Control Strategy

For the DC microgrid demonstrator in Terni, a 3-layer control strategy (see Figure 4) is proposed.

Figure 4: The 3 layers of the control and optimisation algorithm.

For the local control, the proposed control strategy is the virtual impedance method (Jami, Shafiee, & Bevrani, 2018), (Li, Chaudhary, Savaghebi, Vasquez, & Guerrero, 2017), illustrated in Figure 5 (Thomas, S., & S., 2016).

This strategy can assure an autonomous system stability for small variation of the load and generation current. The local controller can set the operation point of the node (the reference value for the current controlled loop) along a droop voltage curve, depending on the DC bus voltage. The first control layer can be operated without communication with the central controller.

Figure 5: The proposed voltage droop control method, based on virtual impedance.

The second control layer is implementing an Optimum Power Flow (OPF) configuration, by setting the droop curve parameters for each local controller, corresponding to a pre-determined power flow distribution between the sources and the loads. This strategy is implemented by a central controller which calculates the optimum power distribution (using certain optimisation criteria) and communicates with the local controllers.

The central controller uses parameter inputs from external sources, such as consumption or generation forecasting algorithms. The second control layer can include a simple optimisation algorithm, such as using the battery to maximise the self-consumption from the PV. The third control layer is implemented in a more complex computing environment, for an advanced optimisation (multi-objective and multi parameter inputs) of the power flows. The third control layer can use solar generation forecasting for optimising consumption and for planning grid services, as well as user habits and machine learning for implementing smart EV charging.

5.2 Protection Strategy

The protection strategy in a DC microgrid has to take into account the main differentiating factor between an AC and a DC power distribution: the low value of line capacitance, resulting in very low latency of the grid. Fault propagation and di/dt values for the short circuit current is much faster than in AC grid (1-3 ms, compared with 10-50 ms). The protection concepts should implement several features, as described in (Jovcic, van Hertem, Linden, Taisne, & Grieshaber, 2011):

1. *Sensitivity*: detection of a faulty link only if a fault is present (avoid nuisance tripping);
2. *Selectivity*: correct identification of faulty grid branches;
3. *Timing*: the total time required to detect a fault and to activate the protection operation must be short enough to prevent equipment damage;
4. *Reliability*: the protection scheme performs correctly by considering main and backup criteria;
5. *Seamless operation*: after the fault clearance, the remaining part of the system continues to operate normally;
6. *Resilience*: detection of faults even in case of partial operation mode and selectivity from any operational events.

There are several methods than can be combined to avoid damages and expensive repairs to the grid converters and loads:

1. *Over-size the converters*. If the current capability of the converters is comparable with the estimated fault current, a high current caused by a fault will not damage the equipment. However, this method requires expensive, bulkier converters, and steady state operation in a lower efficiency regime.
2. *Use fuses*. This strategy has low implementation cost, but implies longer down times, when a fault occurs. The fuses need to be physically replaced.
3. *Use DC circuit breakers*. Although the breakers are more expensive than the fuses, they can have automatic disconnection and re-connection capabilities, allowing minimum down times and automatic reconfiguration, as well as remote control.

The initial protection configuration proposed for the Terni demonstrator is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The proposed protection configuration; (a) fuses, (b) DC circuit breakers.

5.3 Grounding Configuration

The grounding strategy represents the choice of grounding connections and grounding device (resulting in the grounding impedance). There are three different grounding configurations defined for DC microgrids (Mohammadi et al., 2019), based on the position of the ground connection of the DC bus and the conductive parts of the system. These configurations are identified by double letter names TN, TT, and IT. The first letter shows how the source bus is grounded and the second letter shows how the conductive parts are grounded. The letters T, N, and I represent ground connection (Terre), neutral connection, and isolation from both the neutral and the ground, respectively, as shown in Figure 7 (Kakigano, Miura, & Ise, 2010; Xie, Ning, Huang, Jia, & Jian, 2013; Salomonsson, Soder, & Sannino, 2009).

Figure 7: DC microgrid grounding systems.

- **TN**: This is the most recommended grounding configuration for dc microgrids (Kakigano et al., 2010), in which the converter middle point is connected to the ground, and the device enclosure is connected to the neutral and protective earth.
- **TT**: In this configuration, both the converter middle point and the device enclosure are grounded at multiple points.
- **IT**: In this set-up, the neutral point of the grid forming converter is grounded through a large resistance (or not at all), and the device enclosure is grounded separately (Xie et al., 2013).

The *IT* configuration has been widely used in Telecommunication power systems (Salomonsson et al., 2009). *IT* configuration with large grounding resistance is used in both isolated and non-isolated unipolar dc distribution systems.

As we do not see the need for special grounding requirements for the DC microgrid demonstrator, we propose the TN grounding configuration to be implemented.

6 Proposed Converters and Specifications

The proposed microgrid configuration considers five power converters, for implementing the functionalities described in Section 3.

- Isolated unidirectional DC/DC boost converter, for PV connection;
- Non-isolated bidirectional buck/boost converter, for battery connection;
- Non-isolated bidirectional buck/boost converter, for EV charging;
- Grid-feeding inverter (active front end with grid-feeding capability);
- Grid-forming inverter, for AC critical loads support.

6.1 Isolated Unidirectional DC/DC Boost Converter

The photovoltaic generator is implemented by using strings of panels connected in series, for a total open circuit voltage of around 400 V. For the power specifications, several strings are connected in parallel. For demonstration purposes, in the Terni microgrid, the total power of the PV system is 5 kW. We propose to connect this array to the 700 V DC bus using an isolated full-bridge boost converter, with the nominal power of 25 kW. In our demonstrator, the PV array has a peak power of 5 kW. Therefore, the converter operation will not be very efficient, but the system will be ready for additional PV panels, up to a power of 25 kWp.

The PV generator is usually operated in a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) mode. One way to implement this functionality is to control the input voltage and to measure the current provided by the PV panel array. The feedback loop will regulate the input voltage such that the power generated by the system is maintained at around the maximum point for a given sun exposure. On the other hand, the converter is connected to the 700 V DC bus. Therefore, the converter will follow the bus voltage, and will work in current control mode, such that it will transfer the generated PV power to the grid. For this, the PV converter should allow voltage-controlled operation at the input, and current controlled operation at the output.

The proposed PV converter is from the Zekalabs RedPrime DC/DC Converters range, as described by the specifications in Table 1.

Table 1: Specifications of the PV converter.

Feature	Value	Unit
Nominal power	25	kW
DC voltage range (both sides)	0-800	V
Max DC current (both sides)	60	A
Efficiency	95	%
Weight	35	kg
Size	432 x 440.5 x 117	mm

The converter has also other several features: galvanic isolation, bidirectional, integrated pre-charging circuit, Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) filter and contactors. Also, the converter can be controlled/monitored through the following communication interfaces: MODBUS RTU over RS485, MODBUS TCP/IP, CANBUS, PROFIBUS.

Figure 8: Zekalabs RedPrime Isolated DC-DC Converter 25 kW, 60 A.

6.2 Bidirectional DC/DC Buck/Boost Converter

As an energy buffer, a battery bank is proposed for power balancing, for use cases with increased penetration of renewable energy sources like photovoltaic systems. The battery must be connected to the 700 V DC bus and the power flow is controlled by a bidirectional DC/DC converter for charging/discharging operation. In the proposed configuration, this converter is selected for the nominal power of 40 kW, 400 V voltage on the low side (battery) and 700 V on the high side (DC grid voltage).

For the proposed buck/boost converter, the controller should enable closed loop operation and subsequently integration into the grid. In grid-connected mode, the converter follows the DC bus voltage, and controls the charging or discharging current of the battery. The battery voltage will vary, depending on the battery state of charge. The reference for the current controller is obtained from the corresponding power set-point calculated by the energy management system. For the operation of the hybrid grid in the islanded mode, the converter is operated in voltage-controlled mode, setting the voltage of the main DC bus according to a reference. For the demonstrator, it was proposed a Zekalabs RedPrime DC/DC converter, with the characteristics in Table 2.

Table 2: Specifications of the battery converter.

Feature	Value	Unit
Nominal power	40	kW
DC voltage range (low voltage side)	10-700	V
Max DC current (low voltage side)	120	A
DC voltage range (high voltage side)	60-750	V
Max DC current (high voltage side)	60	A
Efficiency	98	%
Weight	28.5	kg
Size	350 x 400 x 186	mm

This converter is also bidirectional as required, with forced air cooling. The communication with the converter can be done through several communication interfaces: MODBUS RTU over RS485, MODBUS TCP/IP, CANBUS, PROFIBUS.

Figure 9: Zekalabs RedPrime DC/DC converter 40 kW, 120 A.

The smart EV charger will be provided by EMOT, the responsible partner for electric mobility in Italian pilot site; EMOT will redesign one of its commercial fast EV chargers to be connected to the 700 V DC bus. Practically, this upgrade will be implemented by replacing the AC/DC converter normally used in a DC charger, with a bidirectional buck/boost DC/DC converter. This device should have similar operating regime with the battery converter.

When the EV is charging, the EV Battery Management System (BMS) will monitor the battery temperature, limiting the charging current to avoid unsafe conditions for the battery. The maximum charging power of the proposed EV charger is 40 kW. If the EV BMS allows higher charging powers (above the 40 kW limit), the converter in the EV charger will switch in the current control mode, regulating the current from the DC bus, such that the power does not exceed the maximum value.

In the V2G mode, the converter will regulate the current provided to the DC bus, according to the setting from the power flow optimization algorithm, while adjusting the input current from the battery, such that the discharge power matches the value transferred to the DC grid. Again, the battery voltage will be variable, depending on the state of charge.

6.3 Grid Following Inverter

In the proposed configuration of the hybrid AC/DC grid demonstrator, the DC microgrid is connected to the AC grid through two identical Active Front End (AFE) inverters. A three-phase inverter modified by AIT (AIT Smart Grid Converter (ASGC)) was selected for this function, interfacing the 400 V AC bus with the 700 V DC bus. For the grid-connected scenario, the AFE are operated as AC current sources, i.e., in the grid-feeding mode. The inverter exchanges real and reactive power components with the AC system at the point of common coupling and stabilizes the DC bus voltage to 700 V. The active and reactive power exchanged with the AC side is controlled by the internal loop of the device, as designed by the AIT team.

The grid-feeding control concept could implement two current control loops, for the d- and q-current component respectively. When the hybrid grid is fully operational, the power is usually transferred from the AC grid to the DC microgrid. In this regime, the inverter output should regulate the DC bus voltage and provide the net current required by the DC loads (if the PV generation and battery discharge does not cover the consumption). The ASGC is bidirectional, with the main specifications presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Specifications of the ASGC.

Feature	Value	Unit
Nominal power	34.5	kW
DC voltage range	570-1,000	V
Max DC current	60	A
Size	432 x 440.5 x 177	mm

Figure 10: AIT Smart Grid Converter.

6.4 Grid Forming Inverter

As proposed in the hybrid grid demonstrator concept, the DC microgrid includes support for AC critical loads (existing appliances that cannot be replaced by their DC equivalent). A grid-forming inverter with a nominal power of 25 kW is proposed. The inverter is operated as a voltage source, so the inverter should be able to regulate the amplitude and the frequency of the load voltage in the presence of disturbances in the load current. The inverter's specifications are listed in Table 4

Table 4: Specifications of the grid forming converter.

Feature	Value	Unit
Nominal power	25	kW
AC voltage range (three-phase)	400-480	V
DC voltage range	0 - 800	V
Maximum current (AC and DC)	60	V
Efficiency	95	%

This inverter is bidirectional, it has galvanic isolation, air cooling, as well as contactors and integrated components for pre-charging and EMC filtering.

Figure 11: RedPrime Isolated AC-DC Converter 25 kW, 800 V.

The basic version of the proposed converter may not have the grid forming capability. However, the converter supplier can add this feature at request.

7 Conclusions

The proposed DC microgrid configuration and converters will be implemented to demonstrate the benefits for renewable and EV charging integration and the power flow optimisation capability of the DC voltage droop control algorithm. Several converters were selected, based on the proposed functional features of the DC microgrid. The system should allow local adjustment of power consumption, as well as seamless power transfer between the DC and the AC branches of the hybrid grid. The overall power flow optimisation will be assured by the communication between the DC central or local controllers and the Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) system that is managing the AC grid stability and operation.

The next steps will include system modeling and simulation of the DC microgrid, using the parameters of the proposed converters. The simulation results will be used to assess the suitability of the proposed configuration for the targeted objectives, and further optimisation of the system design can be performed. This step may include changes of the converters proposed for certain tasks (battery connection, grid forming inverter, etc.).

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